

NanoRevolution in Agriculture: Unveiling NanoPesticides for Sustainable Crop Protection and Beyond"

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ABSTRACT

Nanotechnology has greatly revolutionized in the field of agriculture for manufacturing of pesticides because of their low toxicity, controlled release, high solubility in aqueous solvent, and maintaining the nutritional content of crops. Various nanoformulations such as polymer based (starch, gelatin, lignin), lipid encapsulations, and greener encapsulation have been used in manufacturing of nanopesticides. The active ingredients of nanopesticides are released by diffusion and dissolution methods and their effectiveness mainly depend on the concentration of the active ingredient and the release rate of nanocarriers. Many of the metallic nanopesticides have been formulated such as oxides and hydroxide of zinc, copper, silver, titanium, etc. Moreover, solid nanocarrier based pesticides have also been developed which contains silica, diatomaceous earth, alumina and nanoclays as their active ingredients. Microorganism such as *Bacillus thuringiensis* has also been formulated using nanotechnology to form nanobiopesticides because this bacterium contains cry gene which shows insecticidal activity. Many of the non-target organisms such as fish, amphibians, annelids (earthworm) also get affected by nanopesticides so release of these nanocarriers should be target specific. Moreover, nanopesticides also impose toxic effects to human and environment so great considerations and assessments should be made for their use. Thus, such nanopesticides should be manufactured that are environment friendly and non-toxic for human health

Keywords:

Nanopesticides, Crop Protection, NanoRevolution, Nanoemulsion, Nanoformulation.

INTRODUCTION

Due to rapid increase in world population, there is a huge demand of food crops which ultimately leads to the large use of insecticides and pesticides to control pests and other plant pathogens. As we know that, bacterial and fungal pathogens can cause great loss in quality and yield of crops. To control

these pathogens mostly synthetic chemicals are used which not only destroy harmful pathogens but are also toxic to the useful plants and the environment. About 90 % of the pesticide applied to crops is released in the environment which is toxic for humans [1]. Chemical pesticides such as organochlorines, organophosphates, organo-carbonates and carbamates can cause disease

resistance in plants, reduce their ability to fix nitrogen and also disturbs the soil microflora. Now a days, great advancements have been done in agriculture sector by implementation of nanotechnology for manufacturing of pesticides. Nanopesticides contain nanoparticle formulations that range in size from 100nm to about 1000nm. Nanoparticles of 100nm has such properties that are not present in non-nanoscale particles. Nanoparticles of copper, zinc, silver are effectively used in manufacturing of nano-pesticides. Such nano-formulations should be used in making pesticides that should be remain stable and potentially active in the environment. These nano-pesticides effectively penetrate in the bacteria and fungus and destroy them.

Fig. 1. Nanoparticles for Pest Management [52]

Many parameters such as size, shape, crystalline structure, chemical composition is considered for synthesizing nanoparticles in order to manufacture pesticides. Nanoparticles are mostly formed from natural materials by changing their composition in form of emulsions, dispersions, metallic oxides, polymers etc [2]. Pesticides involving nanoformulations has following advantages [3].

- Nanopesticides are more soluble in water as compared to synthetic chemical pesticides.
- Nanoformulations increased the stability of pesticides when they are sprayed on crops.
- Active particles from nanopesticides are slowly released which effectively kill the pests.
- Nanoformulations prevents the early degradation of a pesticide.
- Nanopesticides have high degree of insecticidal activity because of their smaller particle size and high surface area.

Polymer based nanomaterials to manufacture pesticides are derived from biodegradable polymers. Nanoencapsulation is also an effective method to make pesticides. Plant pathogenic fungi is highly resistant to chemical pesticides so mostly nanoformulations of copper, silver and titanium are used to kill them. Fungal species of Xanthomonas and Pseudomonas are mostly removed from plant crops by nano-silver particles [4]. Copper based nanoformulations are mostly used to kill bacterial species.

SIGNIFICANCE OF NANOPESTICIDES OVER CONVENTIONAL PESTICIDES

Conventional pesticides face severe challenges as they effectively kill the pest but slow down the yield of crops. Moreover, the chemicals used for formulation of these pesticides were highly toxic for the plant as well as for the environment. Conventional pesticides had low solubility in the aqueous solvent, and they were released in the environment in uncontrolled fashion. On the other hand, nanopesticides are synthesized in such a form of nanocarriers that they are released in a controlled manner. Nanopesticides also do not highly contaminate the environment as compare to the conventional pesticides. The main reason for this was that only 0.1% of the pesticide killed the pests whereas 99.9% of the chemicals were released in the surrounding environment. The chemically formulated pesticides also disturbed the nutritional content of crops. Besides, that chemical pesticides also cause a huge loss in biodiversity and ultimately the resistance of pests to that pesticide.

NANOCARRIERS FOR PESTICIDE FORMULATION

Nanocarriers are basically nanomaterials which are used as a transport module for other substances. Pesticide formulations require nanocarriers for their effective delivery to plant crop and ultimately to the digestive tract of that pest to kill it permanently. These nanocarriers protect the nanopesticides from high temperature and other extreme environmental conditions. These nanocarriers also increase the dispersion of nanopesticides on the crops. Following are some properties of these nanoformulations:

- They are easily biodegradable.
- They have high resistance against temperature.
- They have high affinity towards the target pest and pathogen.

Adsorptive interactions are present between the nanocarrier and the pesticide [5]. An antagonistic effect is present between a herbicide (Diclofop-methyl) and silver nanoparticles in which herbicide reduced the concentration of silver from these nanocarriers and this promotes the growth of *Arabidopsis thaliana* [6]. The nanocapsules are composed of a membranous structure that contains nanoparticles. This encapsulation is necessary for an effective release of the nanomaterials.

POLYMER-BASED ENCAPSULATION

Nanomaterials consisting of polymer encapsulation are environment friendly because of their enhanced biodegradable nature. Natural and synthetic polymers such as polyethylene glycol, cellulose, chitosan etc. do not generate toxic by-products and are used as nanoencapsulations for pesticides [7]. Polymeric nanoformulations are non-toxic to both human and environment. Nanoencapsulations of polylactic acid (PLA) for imidacloprid are effectively used against phytopathogen vectors [8].

Conventional pesticides contain organic solvents and surfactants which are hazardous to human health so polymeric encapsulations are a great alternative for this. Depending on the release of nanopesticides, the polymeric formulations can be granule based, water dependent, microcapsules etc. The nanomaterial should be slowly released from the polymeric nanoformulation of the pesticide for effective killings of the insects and other pests. Microspheres of poly-capped polydopamine for an insecticide imidacloprid enhance the release of drug to kill pests [9]. The fabricated polymeric nanoformulations of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) are used for the slow release of glyphosate herbicide [10].

LIPID NANOMATERIAL-BASED ENCAPSULATION

Lipid nanomaterials are also used for pesticide formulations and have effective release mechanism because of their non-toxicity, physiochemical stability and specific target-oriented pest killing. Lipid nanocarriers for formulation of pesticides include solid lipid nanocarriers (SLC), nanoemulsions and non-structures lipid carriers (NLC) [11]. Lipid nanocarriers are used to prevent the photodegradation of pesticides. They are mostly used when pesticide has to be produced on a large scale. The lipid portion of nanocarriers deeply penetrates into plant root and stems to target the pests. The lipid based nanoemulsions penetrate faster into roots taking only one day as compare to nonstructured lipid carriers which take 3 days and solid lipid nanocarriers which take 6 days [12].

The solid lipid nanocarriers do not show any phytotoxic effects during germination of Zea mays but polymeric chitosan does not show effective germination of the plant. The insertion of Eucalyptus citriodora oil in liposome-nanoformulation exhibits an antimicrobial activity against Staphylococcus aureus [13].

CLAY NANOMATERIAL-BASED ENCAPSULATION

Clay based nanoformulations are used for effective adsorption and slow release of hydrophobic components of a pesticide. Nanoformulations based on clay has following properties: [14]

They have large surface area.

- They have high charge density.
- They are hydrophilic in nature.

The incorporation of organic cations with clay nanoformulations enhance the plant adsorption capacity for pesticides such as alachlor, acetochlor, metolachlor. Positively charged silica nanoparticles are used to deliver anionic pesticide such as 2,4-D sodium salt [15]. Silica microcapsules cross-linked with pectin increase the loading capacity of kasugamycin by 20% in order to effectively kill the pathogens [16]. The silica nanoparticles in mesoporous form increase the loading capacity of a pesticide chlorantraniliprole by 42%. These nanoformulations cause mortality of larvae of Plutella xylostella even after 14 days [17].

GREENER ENCAPSULATIONS

Metallic nanoparticles have negative effects on environmental microorganisms which are responsible for oxidation of ammonia and production of nitrification enzymes. Non-toxic nanomaterials such as starch and chitin are used to make nanoformulations of pesticides. These nanomaterials reduce the environmental risk because of their biodegradable nature. Starch based

nanocarriers are used for effective delivery of the pesticide to plant crop to kill pathogens [18] Starch nanoparticles are produced from starch granules by the process of acid-hydrolysis.

Microorganism such as cyanobacteria are also used as nanocarriers because of their biocompatible nature. Cyanobacteria is used as nanocarrier for delivery of a pesticide avermectin and stimulates the slow release of pesticide when it is sprayed in a low quantity [19]. Microalgae can also be used to increase the pesticide load on plant crops to kill pests.

Mechanism of Release of Nanopesticides

The mechanisms used for release of nanopesticides include diffusion, dissolution, biodegradation and osmotic pressure involving a specific pH. In most of the polymeric nanoformulations of the pesticide, the active component reaches to the plant crop and ultimately to the pest in order to kill it by the process of diffusion. Micelle formation of the lipid nanomaterials are also very important in the controlled release of pesticides and other active ingredients. Hydrophobic region of micelles is used to store active ingredients whereas hydrophilic part of the micelle maintains the aqueous stability and steric stability of the nanocarriers [20].

The rate of nanopesticides release depends upon following factors:

- The rate of the release of nanopesticides mainly depends on the interaction and bonding between the nanocarriers and the active fraction of the pesticide. If the interactions are much stronger then release rate of nanopesticides will be much slower [21].
- The release mechanisms also depend on the physiochemical properties of the nanocarriers. If the polymeric nanoformulations are more hydrophobic in nature, then there will be slow-release rate of the pesticide.
- If there is higher water-solubility, then release rate of pesticide will be higher.

The pesticide can also be released in the form of granules. This has an advantage that pesticide provides a long-lasting effect.

FACTORS AFFECTING ACTIVITY OF NANOPESTICIDES

The factors affecting the activity of nanopesticides includes the environmental conditions such as temperature, sunlight, humidity, pH etc.

- The activity of pesticide also depends on the ability of pests and pathogens to tolerate the toxic effect of pesticides.
- The effectiveness of the pesticide also depends on the size, chemical and biological properties of nanocarriers.
- The reactivity of nanomaterials also depends on the surface to volume ratio [22].
- Rod-shaped nanoparticles have more toxic effect as compared to the spherical-shaped nanomaterials [23].
- Temperature also controls the pesticide release in such a way that pesticide loss is decreased during rainfall and effectively kills the pests on weeds.

TYPES OF NANOPESTICIDES

There are various types of nanopesticides such as nanoemulsions, nanodispersions, metallic nanopesticides, solid particle nanopesticides etc. These types of nanopesticides are explained as below.

NANOEMULSIONS

Pesticide nanoemulsions basically consist of an emulsion of oil and water. In this case pesticide is scattered as nanoscale droplets in the presence of various surfactants. Nanoemulsions are the type of nanopesticides which are used to deliver such nanoformulations which are poorly soluble in water. Nanoemulsions have high solubility in the plant crops. Moreover they have 5-10% concentration of surfactants [24].

Nanoemulsions also increase the capacity of the uptake of active ingredients by the plant crops. The glyphosate nanoemulsions show more effect on plant crops to kill pests as compared to non-nanoemulsions. These nanoemulsions are made with various concentrations of methyl esters and organosilicones.

Nanoemulsions are of following two types: [25].

- **Thermodynamically stable nanoemulsions** are formed when non-polar pesticides are partially soluble in aqueous solvent and a high concentration of surfactant is present in the aqueous phase. This type of nanopesticide is stable under a wide range of temperatures.
- **Kinetically stable nanoemulsions** are formed when pesticide is completely insoluble in the aqueous solvent. These types of nanoemulsions of pesticides are not stable under a wide range of temperatures.

NANODISPERSIONS

In this type of pesticides, the solid nanosized particles of the pesticide is dispersed in the aqueous solvent. Nanodispersions are stabilized in water because of their small size and presence of surfactant molecules. Nanodispersions of particle size about 200nm in diameter have long term stability whereas the nanodispersions of diameter 50nm are more soluble in water. This type of pesticide is more kinetically stable as it cannot tolerate wide range of temperatures [26].

Nanodispersions can be easily made by milling process in which solid pesticide is finely grinded into a nanoparticle size powder and this powder is further mixed with the aqueous solvent. Nanodispersions can also be formed by precipitation method in which pesticide is dissolved in a non-polar solvent and this solution is mixed with a polar liquid containing surfactant. The presence of surfactant cause precipitation of the pesticide in form of nanodispersions.

POLYMER BASED NANOPESTICIDES

Polymeric nanopesticides are composed of nanocarriers of natural or synthetic polymers such as starch, chitin, gelatin, alginate, albumin etc. They are easily soluble in water. These nanoformulations plays an important role in release of pesticides by diffusion process. Polymer based nanopesticides are formed by spray drying, melt dispersion, and emulsion diffusion. Many insecticide formulations

have been developed amphiphilic copolymers of polyethylene glycol. The release rate of this insecticide can be increased by increasing the molecular weight of ethylene glycol.

Following are some of the formulations of polymer based nanopesticides:

NANOSPHERES

Nanospheres are the polymer based nanoformulations that contain a colloidal matrix which is filled with active nanocarriers having the ability to get adsorbed on the plant roots to kill pests. The pesticide lansuimamibe B is unstable in environment and it is difficult to dissolve it in aqueous solvent, so polymer based nanoformulations of this pesticide in form of colloidal matrix increase the activity of nanocarriers [27].

NANOGELS

Nanogels are formulation that contains a hydrophilic polymer network. These nanoformulations are mostly composed of either biopolymers or synthetic polymers. These nanoformulations are insoluble in water and are not affected by humidity. Pheromones which are biologically control agents, they can be immobilized by the help of nanogels. The rapid evaporation of the pesticide was reduced by this nanogel formulation. Oils extracted from *L. sidoides* in form of nanogels have extensive bactericidal and fungicidal properties.

Nanogels made up of chitosan can increase the effectiveness of antifungal treatments based on copper. This helps in even distribution of the fungicide on leaves and long-term release of copper. The complex of chitosan and copper effectively inhibits the growth of *Fusarium graminearum* [28].

ELECTROSPUN NANOFIBERS

Nanofibers are tiny fibers in nanometer range which are used to avoid the release bursts of a nanopesticide when it is not evenly distributed on the plant matrix. Nanofibers made up of polyamide or cellulose acetate can uniform release of the pheromones [29].

A nanofiber network made up of polylactic acid and cellulose nanocarriers containing thiamethoxam can efficiently kill a whitefly in 9 days [30].

BACILLUS THURINGIENSIS BASED NANOPESTICIDES:

Pesticides based on living organisms to kill harmful pests and pathogens are known as biopesticides. *Bacillus thuringiensis* can be used to make nanoparticles and nanocomposites by reducing the size of bacterium and using this microorganism as a pesticide. *Bacillus thuringiensis* contains cry gene which synthesizes cry protein having an insecticidal activity. This microorganism produces Bt toxins which are used to kill many insects such as *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Ostrinia nubilalis*, *Spodoptera exigua*, etc [31]. The Bt strains have been improved to increase the intrinsic toxicity of the bacterium. Osmotic

When Bt crystals are sprayed on plant crops, these crystals are ingested by the insect larvae. These crystals get activated inside the gut by proteases and production of endotoxins. These toxins bind to the epithelial cells of the gut which causes pore formation and disturbs the osmotic balance. This results in cell disruption and ultimately the death of larvae in 2-3 days [32]. *B. Thuringiensis* can be made into nanoform by lysing the bacterial cells and making ultrafine powder containing nanoparticles by the process of high-pressure homogenization. The homogenized Bt nanoparticles

of size 1.9 μm are effectively used to kill the diamondback moth as compared to the unhomogenized Bt nanopesticides [33]. The Bt nanopesticide is sprayed on plant crops along with many adhesives to provide affinity for the attachment on plant cells and also protects the nanopesticide from U.V light. Nanopesticides of Bt strains also contain many metallic oxides and inorganic nanocarriers for better formulation of the pesticides. The Bt biopesticides containing zinc oxide nanoparticles are used to kill pulse beetle i.e., *Callosobruchus maculatus* with 100% mortality rate [34].

METAL NANOPESTICIDES

Many of the metallic oxides of silver, copper, titanium oxide, are considered as antimicrobial agents. This antimicrobial property is mainly due to their crystalline structure and high surface to volume ratio. The metallic nanoparticles used to formulate pesticides are less toxin in nature and are safe for environment. The Trichoderma mediated selenium nanoparticles have been synthesized to treat the downy mildew disease in pearl millet [35].

The metallic nanoparticles cause the killing of the pest by following way: [36].

- When metallic nanocarriers in a pesticide absorb light, photocatalysis occurs which leads to the release of superoxide radicals. These radicals cause oxidation of proteins and nucleic acids of bacteria, fungi and other pests and ultimately kills them.
- Disruption of the pathogen or pest cell membrane leading to the release of contents and death of cell.
- Metallic ions are uptake by pathogenic cells which disturbs the replication of DNA.

SILVER

Pesticides based on silver nanocarriers have great bactericidal and viricidal capacity because of their low toxicity and high surface area of crystalline structure.

Pesticides containing silver nanoformulations are used to kill phytopathogen *Raffaelea* and prevents it from causing oak wilt [37]. The silver nanoparticles help in preventing pest resistance and environmental pollution. *Serratia* sp has the ability to synthesize silver nanoparticles which has an antifungal activity for *Bipolaris sorokiniana* causing disease in wheat (Morones et al., 2005). Silver nanoparticles can effectively degrade the wood degrading fungi. Graphene oxide-silver nanoformulations can be used to degrade spore of *Fusarium graminearum* [38].

TITANIUM OXIDE

Titanium oxide shows great antibacterial effectiveness against *Xanthomonas perforans* that bacterial diseases in tomato. This titanium oxide based nanopesticides helps in the increase in yield of tomatoes [39]. The light rays containing photons are absorbed by the titanium oxide nanocarriers that results in release of superoxide radicals and ultimately the killing of pest. These metallic nanocarriers are environment friendly and non-toxic.

COPPER

Copper nanoparticles encapsulated with gelatin are mostly used for formulation of pesticides that are effective against gram-positive bacteria and gram-negative bacteria. Copper based

nanopesticides also have toxic effect on *E. coli* by causing lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation and DNA degradation [40]. Copper based fungicides has also been developed against fungal phytopathogens.

Nanocopper based pesticides are also used to treat pomegranate bacterial blight. These nanocarriers kill the pest in even small concentration [41].

SOLID NANOPESTICIDES

Solid nanopesticides involving the nanoformulations of silica, alumina, clay mostly effects the wax coating on the insect cuticle. The abrasion in insect cuticle causes the water loss and ultimately the death of pest due to dessication. Following are some examples of solid nanoformulation based pesticides.

SILICA

The silicon nanoparticles are effectively used against rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* because of their lipophilic nature. These solid nanoparticles showed their effect for atleast two months [42]. Silica based nanoformulations kills the insect by disrupting the cuticular lipids. They are also used to inhibit the fungal growth on cereal plants. Silica nanocarriers also helps in the slow release of pesticides for effective killing of the pests.

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles of size 2-50 nm are used for controlled and effective release of a fungicide i.e., metalaxyl.

DIATOMACEOUS EARTH (DE)

Nanoformulations containing diatomaceous earth are mainly composed of amorphous silica and are used to protect stored grains from insect pests. Nanoformulations of DE mixed with plant extract bitterbarkomycin are effectively used against a grain pest *Rhyzopertha dominica* [43]. The DE nanopesticide gets absorbed in epicuticular lipids are results in death of pest by dessication.

The main drawback of using this pesticide nanoformulations is that they are required in high quantity to kill the pests which affects the grain properties.

CLAY

Nanoclay formulations are 1mm thin sheets of silicate materials used to make nanopesticides. These types of pesticides are biodegradable and have low toxicity. Clay based nanoformulations are mostly derived from volcanic ash. These nanoformulations effectively control the release of a herbicide 2, 4-dichlorophenoxyacetate [44]). The nanoclay formulations are mostly used for target delivery of pesticides and fungicides.

ALUMINA

Mostly alumina dusts are used to protect stored grains. Nanocarriers of aluminium has been used as insecticide formulation against *S. oryzae* and *R. dominica*. These two grain pests are highly susceptible to nanoformulations of aluminium [45].

The nanoformulations of aluminium shows insecticidal activity based upon physical process rather than biochemical process. Nanostructured alumina also has potential to induce mortality in leaf-cutting ants, i.e., *Acromyrmex lobicornis*. They are also used to treat Fusarium root rot in tomato crops.

APPLICATIONS AGAINST PLANT PATHOGENS

Nanopesticides are used against plant pathogens and pests such as bacteria, fungi, viruses and insects. The details of pathogens susceptible to nanopesticides are given as below: [46].

BACTERIA

Some of the nanocarriers showing bactericidal activity in form of pesticides are explained as below:

- The nanopesticides containing **zinc oxide** nanoformulations are more effective against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.
- The nanofilms of **chitosan** has antimicrobial effect against phytopathogen *Xylella fastidiosa*.
- The nanoformulations of **titanium oxide** prevents the bacterial infection in cucumber by *P. syringae*.
- The nanoformulations of **magnesium oxide** also has strong bactericidal activity against gram-negative bacteria and spore-forming bacteria.

FUNGI

Some of the nanocarriers showing fungicidal activity in form of pesticides are explained as below:

- The nanoformulations of **silver** have strong fungicidal activity against perennial ryegrass. This fungicide mainly inhibited the colony formation.
- The **zinc oxide** nanoparticles show high effectiveness against *Fusarium graminearum*. These nanoparticles also inhibit the hyphal formation of *Penicillium expansum*.
- The nanoparticles of **cuprous oxide** are sprayed on tomato crops to kill *Phytophthora infestans*.
- The nanoparticles of **quantum dots** are also used to inhibit the hyphal growth and germination.

INSECTS

Some of the nanocarriers showing insecticidal activity are explained as below:

- **Avermectin** is an insecticide that kills the insects by affecting the process of neurotransmission.
- The nanoparticles of **polyethylene glycol** containing essential oil of garlic has strong insecticidal activity against *Tribolium castaneum*.
- The nanocarriers of alumina are mostly used against *S. oryzae*.

ECOTOXICOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF NANOPESTICIDES

Besides the advantages of nanopesticides to kill harmful pathogens and pests, they also affect the non-target species. Ecotoxicological effects means the changes in biological state of microorganisms on the exposure to chemicals.

Plants

Nanopesticides also have ecotoxicological effects on many of the non-target plant species. The permethrin nanopesticide have toxic effect on seed germination and root length in many of the plant species such as *Zea mays*, *Lycopersicum esculentum* etc [47].

The atrazine polymeric nanopesticides also have toxic effects on non-target maize plants. The copper hydroxide nanopesticides also have toxic effects on lettuce plant i.e., *Lactuca sativa*.

SOIL ORGANISMS

When nanopesticides are sprayed on plant crops, these nanocarriers also leach down to soil and effects many of the soil microorganisms. Earthworm (*Lumbricus terrestris*) is the natural burrower of the soil which makes the land fertile. Nanopesticides when leach down to soil have adverse toxic effects on this soil microbe.

Many of the annelids such as *Enchytraeus crypticus* and *Eisenia fetida* are also susceptible to the toxic effect of nanocarriers in pesticides [48]. Many species of the nematodes and arthropods are also affected by nanopesticides. The lipid nanopesticides of atrazine are more toxic to *Caenorhabditis elegans*.

AQUATIC MICROORGANISMS

The nanopesticides also have adverse ecotoxicological effects on aquatic microorganisms. The nanoformulations of pesticides affects both marine and freshwater species. Many of the aquatic species affected include fish i.e., *Oncorhynchus mykiss*. The aquatic specie *Daphnia similis* is also susceptible to the toxicity of nanopesticides [49].

The nanopesticide bifenthrin has adverse effect on *Oncorhynchus mykiss*. The nanopesticide cypermethrin cause severe cellular damage to liver of *Channa punctatus*. The azoxystrobin nanopesticide also have toxic effect on *Danio rerio* during post fertilization period. The clomazone polymeric nanopesticide also kills the bullfrog tadpoles i.e., *Lithobates catesbeianus*.

AERIAL ORGANISMS

Nanopesticides shows toxic effects on aerial organisms such as *Aedes aegypti*, *Culex tritaeniorhynchus*, *Spodoptera littoralis* and *Blattella germanica* (German cockroach). Many of the non-target organisms such as honeybees, and pollinators are also killed by nanopesticides. Pyrethrum lipid nanopesticides are highly toxic towards honeybee i.e., africanized *Apis mellifera* [50].

ENVIRONMENTAL RISK ASSESSMENT OF NANOPESTICIDES

Environmental risk assessment of nanopesticides means those hazards and impacts on the environment which are imposed by use of nanopesticides. Scientific Advisory Panel of the US Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act (FIFRA) has considered nanoformulations of silver oxides and other metals toxic for environment. The safety assessment of nanopesticides should be done before launching them in the market.

The encapsulated nanoformulation containing the active ingredient of pesticide are easily degraded and released in the environment. The risk assessment of nanopesticides mainly depends on the type of nanoformulation, type of active ingredient, degree of exposure of the active ingredient and the concentration of that active ingredient [51].

During the manufacturing of nanopesticide, it must be thoroughly examined that how the nanocarriers of the pesticide will interact with plant pathogens and also the plant. Nanopesticide showing toxic effect to the pests but also reducing seed germination and causing plant withering should not be allowed to be launched in the market. In the same way, if any metallic nanopesticide is making the soil infertile for further cultivation, then use of that pesticide should be avoided. The fruits and vegetable grown on that pesticide sprayed crops should be examined to ensure that nanocarriers as active ingredients have not become the part of that food material.

TOXICITY OF NANOPESTICIDES

If nanopesticides are sprayed in high concentration in the environment, then they are chances that human may inhale the nanocarriers and may expose to health risks. For this reason, the formulations of nanopesticides should be made in such a way that nanocarriers of pesticides should not be released in the environment for longer time rather they should be biodegradable. If these nanocarriers get adsorbed by human cells, then there is decrease in the viability of cells and morphological changes might occur in the cells.

High concentration of active ingredient also kills the non-target species beside pests. This highly disturbs the biodiversity. Nanopesticides showing toxic effects to green algae, blue green algae and other plants disturbs the natural environmental processes such as photosynthesis, carbon cycle etc. Nanopesticides can also become the part of food chain if they get permanently adsorbed on fruit crops so such formulations should be made that are water soluble and easily washed out before eating. The toxicity of nanopesticides also depends upon the chemical composition and high surface area of the formulated nanocarriers.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

Nanotechnology has greatly advanced in agricultural sector through manufacturing of nanopesticides. These formulations should be used worldwide at low cost so everyone can eat safe, chemical free fruits and vegetables. Under-developed countries should immediately avoid the use of chemical pesticides in order to keep the environment clean and reduce human health risks. The industries synthesizing nanopesticides should highly consider the problem of pest and pathogen resistance and ultimately the killing of non-target and beneficial species. It is seen that polymer based nanoformulation for pesticides are most safe so researchers are trying to get maximum use of polymers such as cellulose, starch etc to formulate nanopesticides as they would be highly environment friendly.

CONCLUSION

To make nanopesticides complete non-toxic to the environment, various essential oils and pheromones are being studied to formulate pesticides using nanocarriers. This would have a great advantage because they are biodegradable in nature. In this way, nanotechnology will have significant and long-term impact in the field of agriculture. All the problems of food security and climate changes would be solved as there will be high agricultural productivity. Just like the *Bt* nanobiopesticides, more microorganisms should be studied that may contain genes that are highly insecticidal only for the targeted pests as they are highly environment friendly.

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